

IMPREGNATION OF BLEACHED JUTE YARNS WITH SYNTHETIC RESINS. PART III. FACTORS INFLUENCING THE WET-STRENGTH

BY R. P. CHATTERJEE, A. GHOSE AND J. K. CHOWDHURY

CHEMICAL LABORATORY, BOSE INSTITUTE, CALCUTTA

(Received February 24, 1954)

Solutions of melamine resin give best improvements of wet-strength after ageing for 72 hours. The resin intermediates form aggregates on standing and ultimately coagulate. The solution is suitable for application when a blue haze appears on standing. The optimum pH for the preparation of melamine-formaldehyde resins lie between 3.0-3.5. At lower pH the polymerisation is too rapid affording little time for suitable treatment whereas at higher pH the resin becomes insoluble. Diammonium hydrogen phosphate has been found to be the most suitable catalyst for melamine and urea resins. It enables the use of a lower temperature for baking resinated yarns. The resin solutions have been applied in 3-4% solid contents.

The effect of different types of resins and methods of application on the wet-strength of bleached yarns have been dealt with in Part I.⁵ Other factors, such as the composition and stability of the resin solutions, curing of the resins and degree of bleaching of yarns have also great effect on the wet-strength. The resins have to be deposited inside the fibres in order to obtain the best results. Deposition on the surface makes the fibre weak. Aqueous solutions of urea and melamine resin intermediates penetrate into the binding materials and on account of their basic character, combine with the free carboxylic groups of bleached jute. High polymers, on the other hand, have a more limited number of free basic groups and on account of the size of the molecules fail to penetrate deep into the binding materials. The role of various factors in the improvement of wet-strength has been discussed in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Stabilisation of solution.—Low-molecular resins form aggregates if the solutions are allowed to stand, and tend to coagulate or form insoluble precipitate. In order to overcome this tendency, attempts were made to stabilise these solutions. The use of gum arabic, pyridine, glycerol, glycol etc. proved only partially successful. The main defects with these reagents were that the yarns became coloured after baking. A better method of stabilisation was found in the control of pH . Both melamine and urea resin solutions were stable at low pH . The yarns had, however, to be thoroughly washed to make them free of acid before baking.

Several samples of yarns, bleached under identical conditions, were taken for resin treatment. The two ends of each sample were carefully fastened so that the twist did not change materially during the treatment. The yarns were kept immersed overnight in aqueous solutions of resin intermediates. The excess of solution was drained off under suction in a Büchner funnel. It was then transferred to a 0.05% solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (curing agent), kept for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, squeezed thoroughly, washed once with water so as to remove any surface deposition of resin, dried and resins were then polymerised *in situ* by heat treatment of resinated yarns.

Curing agents.—Certain constituents of bleached fibres, presumably the hemicelluloses, were discoloured by heat². Attempts were therefore made to reduce the temperature and time of baking by the use of catalysts³ (curing agents). These curing agents enabled the use of a lower temperature for baking and thus reduced discoloration. Initially, the treated yarns were baked at 150° but later with the use of these curing agents, a temperature of 110° was used. Several acids and their salts were tried for their action as curing agents. A large number of experiments were carried out but only a few typical data are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
Effect of curing agents on wet-strength.

Urea-formaldehyde resin (pH 3.0—3.5).		Melamine-formaldehyde resin (pH 3.0—3.5).	
Curing agent.	% Improvement.	Curing agent.	% Improvement.
Boric acid	7.0	Diammonium hydrogen phosphate	62.6
Ammonium chloride	10.0	Sodium dihydrogen phosphate	57.0
Sodium dihydrogen phosphate	11.0	Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate	56.0
Diammonium hydrogen phosphate	17.0	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	52.7
Alum	23.0		

Acid type curing agents like acetic acid, phosphoric acid, boric acid etc. reduced soap washability of impregnated yarns. Some of these agents such as acetic acid were found to impart some gloss to the yarns. The various curing agents might be arranged as follows in order of their activity with regard to melamine resins: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4 > \text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 = (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 > \text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4$.

It might be stated here that the use of these curing agents, particularly of diammonium hydrogen phosphate, enabled a reduction of baking temperature from 150° to 110° (10 minutes). If the temperature be raised to 120°-130°, the time of baking could be reduced to 5 minutes so as to obtain approximately the same improvement of wet-strength.

Effect of p_H .—It has been stated before that both melamine and urea resins form stable solutions at low p_H . If p_H was raised, melamine solution tended to precipitate. At very low p_H , on the other hand, the rate of polymerisation was too high (as deduced from the rapid appearance of the blue haze and coagulation). Melamine resin was therefore prepared at an optimum p_H of 3.0 to 3.5. The blue haze appeared after some 72 hours, allowing sufficient stability to the melamine solution. The resin prepared under these conditions might be called "cationic"⁴ and had considerable affinity for acidic groups present in jute.

TABLE II

Effect of p_H (of the impregnating soln.) on wet-strength.
4% Melamine resin used.

p_H of the soln.	...	1.5	2.8	3.0	3.2	4.4	4.8
%Improvement	...	14.4	19.7	51.6	54.8	17.0	10.4

Urea-formaldehyde resin had a wider range of stability and could be used either in acidic range or in the alkaline.

Ageing of the melamine resin solution.—On allowing a solution of melamine resin to stand at room temperature and appropriate p_H , the solution gradually became thicker, then opalescent and ultimately coagulated. It became necessary to know at what stage of ageing the resin solution would be most suitable for use. It was found that with melamine resins, prepared at p_H 3.2, 72 hours' ageing at room temperature was necessary for the solution to ripen.

TABLE III

Effect of ageing of the m.f. resin solution on wet-strength.

Time of ageing (hrs.)	...	24	48	72	96	144	240	360
%Improvement	...	24.0	42.4	54.2	34.0	30.1	21.5	6.9

The particle size of resins begins to grow on standing and the p_H of the solution begins to fall. If the solution is aged for too long a time the resin particles are deposited on the surface of resinated yarns causing loss of wet-strength.

Optimum concentration.—The resin solutions were next investigated for optimum concentration, keeping p_H and ageing conditions approximately the same. It would be seen from Table IV that 3-4% solution of melamine and urea resins caused maximum improvements in wet-strength. The yarns, however, absorbed only a fraction of the resins present, and gained in weight to the extent of about 2-3% on the weight of the bleached yarns. In view of some loss of weight of bleached yarns in water, the amount of resin actually absorbed by the yarn was determined from the difference in the nitrogen

contents of the impregnated yarns and their bleached controls. About 6-7% of the original weight was lost in bleaching due mainly to the removal of lignin while the weight increased by about 2-3% on impregnation. The net loss of weight of jute yarns caused by bleaching and impregnation came to about 4 to 5%.

TABLE IV

Effect of concentration of impregnating solution on wet-strength.

$p_H = 3.2$ Time of ageing = 72 hours.

Conc.	Urea-formaldehyde.		Melamine-formaldehyde.		
		% Improvement.	Conc.	% Resin absorbed.	% Improvement.
1%	...	9.1	1%	2.04%	20.2
			2.0	2.32	32.5
2	...	14.3	3.5	2.48	52.7
			4.2	2.67	54.2
3.5	...	23.0	5.0	2.68	46.0
			6.5	2.70	34.0
4	...	21.7			
			7.8	2.72	30.0
5	...	15.5			

REFERENCES

1. Feast, *British Plastics*, 1945, 17, 36, 66.
2. Sarkar *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 74.
3. Hodgins *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1941, 33, 769.
4. Wohnsiedler & Thomas, U. S. P. 2, 345, 543, 1944.
5. Chatterjee, Ghose & Chowdhury, *this Journal*, 1954, 17, 155.